

Bypassing NAC - A handy How-to Guide

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Abstract: Bypassing IEEE 802.1X with a transparent bridge solution. Implementation based on NACKered. NAC bypass project available on GitHub. A way to bypass Network Access Control. Feeding in own commands via a legitimate device. Can be used autonomously in environments where devices are switched.

Keywords: Assessment, Bash, Block, Detect, Dominik Altermatt, GitHub, HTTP, ICMP, iptables, Linux

1. Preface

This paper was written in 2019 as part of a research project at scip AG, Switzerland. It was initially published online at <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20190207> and is available in English and German. Providing our clients with innovative research for the information technology of the future is an essential part of our company culture.

2. Introduction

In the article entitled *Network Access Control – What’s important to remember with NAC?* [1], Dominik Altermatt described the basics of *Network Access Control* (NAC) and briefly discussed how to bypass this control mechanism. In this edition of Labs, we will introduce a practical solution for bypassing port-based *IEEE 802.1X* [2] network access control.

3. Standing on the shoulders of giants

In 2011, Alva Lease “Skip” Duckwall IV gave a presentation at *Defcon 19* entitled *A Bridge Too Far* [3] in which he showed how *802.1X* can be bypassed using a *Linux transparent bridge*. Based on these principles, Matt E [4] wrote the bash script *NACKered v2.92.2* [5]. We then used this script to write our own *NAC bypass* [6] script collection, which we have released on our *GitHub page* [7].

At first, the plan was to use *NACKered* and make selective changes as needed. But we gradually found ourselves changing so many things that we ultimately developed a standalone solution. We included one extension to support Laurent Gaffié’s [8] *Responder* [9] tool, because the combination of *NAC bypass* and *Responder* is very useful for internal network-based *penetration tests* or as part of *red team assessments* to gain access to login credentials.

4. Requirements and setup

The basic requirement for an *NAC bypass* is access to a device that has already been authenticated. This device is used to log into the network and then smuggle in network packages from a different device. This involves placing the attacker’s system between the network switch and the authenticated device. One way to do this is with a *Raspberry Pi* [10] and two network adapters.

The *NACKered* script and our *nac_bypass_setup.sh* solution were written and tested on Debian-based Linux distributions, but both should be executable on other Linux distributions as well. The following software packages are required:

- bridge-utils
- macchanger
- arptables, iptables and ebtables
- mii-tool
- tcpdump
- br_netfilter (kernel module)

For arptables, iptables and ebtables, make sure not to use *Netfilter xtable tools* [11] (nft), or the script will not work as *desired* [12].

The *nac_bypass_setup.sh* script has the following parameters:

```
nac_bypass_setup.sh v0.6.1 usage:
-1 <eth>    network interface plugged
into switch
-2 <eth>    network interface plugged
into victim machine
-a          autonomous mode
-c          start connection setup only
-h          display this help
-i          start initial setup only
-r          reset all settings
-R          enable port redirection for
Responder
-S          enable port redirection for
OpenSSH and start the service
```

The parameters -1 and -2 define which network adapters will be used. You can also edit them directly in the script: -a suppresses the output of the script's log and debugging information and no manual interaction is required when running it. The parameters -R and -S activate port forwarding for the use of SSH and Responder. The parameters -c, -i and -r only initiate certain sequences within the script. Their respective functions will be discussed in more detail later.

5. Use

The `nac_bypass_setup.sh` script is used together with a legitimate device as shown in the diagram below:

Figure: Using the NAC bypass

The legitimate device, *client*, is not initially connected to the network switch. Now the script is started on the attacker device, *bypass*. *Bypass* and *attacker* are one physical device. The *attacker* figure symbolizes actions carried out by the attacker on the NAC bypass device. The first step is the initial configuration: To start with, unwanted services, such as *NetworkManager*, are stopped, IPv6 is disabled and any DNS configurations are initialized. Next, the *bridge* is configured and started. To ensure bridging works as desired, the kernel has to be configured to forward *EAPOL frames*. Without this adjustment, 802.1X authentication will not be carried out.

Once the configuration is complete, the network cables can be connected and the bridge's *switch side* is now enabled as a passive forwarder. The *bypass* device forwards all network traffic back and forth between the *switch* and the *client* but cannot send any packets itself. The *client* should now be authenticated with the network switch and can log into the network successfully.

All network traffic passes through the bridge and can be analyzed accordingly. This is done to capture Kerberos and SMB packets with `tcpdump` – as these are normally found in several places on a Windows network, making it possible to see the network configuration, such as the *client's* IP and MAC address. This information is used to automatically configure the *client side* of the bridge. However, the *bypass's* connection to the network remains blocked to ensure that network packets from the attacker device find their way onto the network and are detected. If packets from the *attacker* are sent onto the network later, an *iptables rule* will overwrite the MAC address, meaning that the packets will appear as if they originated from the *client*. The same procedure is implemented using *iptables rules* at IP level, so that outgoing TCP, UDP and ICMP packets also have the same IP address as the *client*. Finally, the *attacker* is able to connect to the network and can carry out actions from their own device.

If port forwarding has been enabled for SSH and Responder, the bridge forwards all requests for the respective ports to the *attacker's* services. From there, a

Responder instance can be run to carry out *multicast poisoning* and to perform authentication for protocols such as *SMB*, *_FTP*, or *HTTP*. This instance can be reached from the network using the *client's* IP address.

6. Bypassing NAC in an infinite loop

The scenario described above is only possible if the attacker is in possession of a legitimate device. But if the attacker only has physical access to a building and its rooms and does not have their own device, additional steps are necessary. If a room has a network installation – e.g. a meeting room or shared workspace – the bypass device can still be installed. However, it must be noted that the NAC bypass setup is agile and can respond to changes such as switching devices. With a shared workspace, for example, User1 connects their device to the docking station in the morning. The hidden bypass device installs its configuration on User1's device. As soon as they leave the shared workspace, the bypass device resets to the initial state and waits for new devices. If User2 connects their device to the docking station, the bypass device is no longer allowed to run with User1's configuration. Instead, it must use User2's credentials to connect to the network.

The bypass device therefore checks network connectivity at certain intervals and then responds to status changes and then invokes the appropriate NAC bypass procedure. We created a simple implementation of this check with the *awareness.sh* [13] script, which checks an adapter's network status every five seconds and responds accordingly when the status changes.

```

while true
do
    NETWORK_STATE_INTERFACE=`cat
"/sys/class/net/$INTERFACE/carrier"`

    if [ "$NETWORK_STATE_INTERFACE" -ne
"$STATE_INTERFACE" ]; then

        STATE_COUNTER=0

        if [ "$NETWORK_STATE_INTERFACE" -eq 1
]; then
            echo "[!] $INTERFACE is now up!"
        else
            echo "[!] $INTERFACE is now
down!"
        fi
        else
            if [ "$STATE_COUNTER" -eq
"$THRESHOLD_UP" ] && [
"$NETWORK_STATE_INTERFACE" -eq 1 ]; then
                echo "[!!] Set new config"
                bash nac_bypass_setup.sh -a -c

                elif [ "$STATE_COUNTER" -eq
"$THRESHOLD_DOWN" ] && [
"$NETWORK_STATE_INTERFACE" -eq 0 ]; then
                    echo "[!!!] Reset config"
                    bash nac_bypass_setup.sh -a -r
                    bash nac_bypass_setup.sh -a -i
                fi

                echo "[*] Waiting"
                ((STATE_COUNTER++))
            fi

STATE_INTERFACE=$NETWORK_STATE_INTERFACE
  
```

```
sleep $TIMER
done
```

First, the basic setup for the NAC bypass is configured. Next, a loop is started to monitor the state of the network interface. The second part of the NAC bypass setup is then executed as soon as the interface is activated. If the network connection is lost, the configuration is reset and initialized. Configurable cycles are also set between the status changes to avoid premature configuration changes when network connectivity is lost temporarily, for example. This script allows a bypass device to respond to device switching; this can be done without any manual intervention over an extended period of time by placing the device in an appropriate room.

7. Next steps

The *awareness.sh* script responds to status changes and modifies the NAC bypass configuration accordingly. All other actions must be carried out manually at present using the likes of SSH on the device. This SSH service is only available on the victim's network, however. One of the next steps is the planned integration of an additional management interface using a WLAN or cellular network adapter. This adapter could then be used to establish an autonomous connection, allowing the attacker to access the device without having to be physically on the premises or network. The *awareness script* could also be enhanced to

include modules that ensure more autonomy. For example, communication via a *command and control server (C2)* can be configured to receive commands or extract data. The *NAC bypass* [14] project is available on GitHub. We appreciate any *feedback* you may have and welcome *pull requests*.

8. External Links

- [1] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20180222>
- [2] <https://1.ieee802.org/security/802-1x/>
- [3] <https://www.defcon.org/images/defcon-19/dc-19-presentations/Duckwall/DEFCON-19-Duckwall-Bridge-Too-Far.pdf>
- [4] <https://github.com/p292>
- [5] <https://github.com/p292/NACKered>
- [6] https://github.com/scipag/nac_bypass
- [7] <https://github.com/scipag>
- [8] <https://g-laurent.blogspot.com/>
- [9] <https://github.com/lgandx/Responder>
- [10] <https://raspberrypi.org/>
- [11] https://wiki.nftables.org/wiki-nftables/index.php/Legacy_xtables_tools
- [12] <https://twitter.com/0x6d69636b/status/1067802857141911552>
- [13] https://github.com/scipag/nac_bypass/blob/master/awareness.sh
- [14] https://github.com/scipag/nac_bypass